

THE SIGNIFICANT ROLE OF TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH FAIRY TALES

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Abstract English is one of leading foreign languages which is taught all over the world and is increasing currently. In addition, new methods are being created for students to learn in a shorter time. This article is analyzing the role of fairy tales in teaching and learning English and what skills are developed with the help of fairy tales.

Key words: fairy tales, core skills, young learners, puppet shows, cardboard, preschool.

Introduction

The main goal of learning and teaching English is to become fluent in English. Nowadays, there are several methods of teaching language to young learners. For example, some language teachers teach through various games, activities, while others prefer to teach with various English songs, movies or videos. Other ones try to find new methods. In this article I am going to introduce teaching and learning English with fairy tales. Teaching English with the usage of fairy tales has tremendous benefit to young kids.

Materials and methods

The staging of fairy tales helps preschoolers to be like brave, strong, resourceful, brave, dexterous heroes, attracts children to the ideological direction of a fairy tale, in which the power of virtue - goodness always ends in victory. The form of narration adopted in a fairy tale, the repeated repetition of the same words and phrases, contributes to the improvement of children's pronunciation in English, thanks to which they retain it well in memory when repeated.

The production of shadow theaters is one of the unique types of puppet shows. He plays with toys made of figures, not dolls. The audience can sit in front of the stage and see the shadows of people, animals and birds moving through the light on the screen. Shadows of people and animals for staging shadow theater children draw and cut themselves. Children should be taught to make figures that move their head and tail, for this the parts are connected with wire and rotated in a spiral position.

Flat and voluminous cardboard puppets take part in productions of cardboard theaters. Unidirectional figures move only in one direction with the help of a rope, wire, etc. In the production of cardboard theaters, forms controlled by a string and wire from above also take part, they can easily move and turn. The stage is made from three pieces of cardboard or plywood.

There are several types of tabletop theater staging: in one, the performance is on a simple stage without a curtain, in another, on a box-shaped stage (cardboard staging), in the third, a flat staging, the stage consists of two parts, from cardboard. The characters in these productions are moved in various ways by hands, pallets, wires, and magnets. The structure of the forms is also different. The work begins with the selection of a fairy tale or parable, and then the corresponding characters are prepared.

Thus, teaching English to preschool children should be conducted as an interesting activity, and not as a duty, and with the help of several effective methods, including theatrical fairy

tales and stories, classes should be organized that will help them in the future, can serve as a basis for learning. Preschool children need to be properly explained how important it is to learn foreign languages in natural conditions. In fact, the child is too small to learn a foreign language itself without any support so fairy tales greatly motivate them to gain the foreign language easily.

Firstly, fairy tales makes learners involve on a fairy world which rises the encouragement of core skills in reading and speaking. We know that fairy tales have a simple sentence structure. The words in it are common and often used. This is convenient for young learners because at the beginning they have difficulty in understanding long texts and translating complex sentences. This leads to boredom. Speaking about impact on development of speaking skills, fairy tales with pictures can be example. Learners may be given a task like illustrating the picture and finding which fairy tales is described in the picture. This leads children to speak. In addition, we can take story telling is an example. Students may tell their classmates their own stories or briefly recount a narrative or story they have already heard from someone. Telling stories encourages original thought. Additionally, it assists pupils with expressing concepts in the beginning, middle and end of a story, along with the necessary characters and backdrop. Students may also tell jokes or riddles. For instance, the teacher might select a few students to tell a few quick jokes or riddles as an introduction at the start of each class section.

By doing so, the instructor will be able to draw the class's attention while also addressing the pupil's speaking abilities.

Conclusion

Children learn linguistic patterns including past tenses, adjectives, comparatives and more through the use of fairy tales. For grammar lessons teachers could use sections from the fairy tale. For instance, you might encourage students to look for irregular verbs, list all adjectives or look for words and phrases that denote place or time. Longer instances of dialogue with a range of punctuation marks are frequently seen in stories that are not possible in grammar practice books. Fairy tales widens the outlook of learners moreover it expands active vocabulary, the main heroes and characters may lead readers to the world of unexplored world of knowledge.

Fairy tales can be effective for learning and teaching English. The using various activities at representing fairy tales are really productive we could utilize effective aspects and approaches to further the learners' proficiency and abilities at learning English.

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